

List of Supplemental Figures

Figure S1. Multi-species coalescent species tree and duplication of Figure 1 for convenient comparison to additional analyses in this supplement.

Figure S2. Multi-species coalescent species tree (as in Fig S1) with full taxon names.

Figure S3. Species tree from concatenated analysis of genes from orthofinder and phylopypruner

Figure S4. Gene concordance values for phylogeny in S3

Figure S5. Bayesian relaxed molecular clock analysis and duplication of Figure 2 for convenient comparison to additional analyses in this supplement.

Figure S6. Bayesian relaxed molecular clock analysis as in S8 showing 95% Highest Posterior Densities at each node.

Figure S7. Sensitivity analysis of divergence time estimates using subsets of genes with Sortadata. We compared results from 15, 20, 25 and 30 genes, keeping all other parameters constant.

Figure S8. Posterior probability values of nodal support from Bayesian analysis using 15 genes selected with sortadata.

Figure S9. Species tree using Multi-species coalescent, using expanded taxon sampling by adding individual mitochondrial genes and duplicate of Figure 3 for convenient comparison to additional analyses in this supplement.

Figure S10. Species tree using Multi-species coalescent and expanded taxon sampling (as in Fig S10) with full taxon names

Figure S11. Species tree from concatenated analysis of only mitochondrial data alone, including 12S, 16S, and co1

Figure S12. Ancestral state reconstruction of presence/absence of bioluminescence in Cypridinidae.

Figure S13. Ancestral state reconstruction of presence/absence of bioluminescent courtship signaling in Cypridinidae.

List of Supplemental Tables

Table S1. Specimen collection and transcriptome sequencing information

Table S2. Length and height of carapaces to tentatively assign species to genera

Table S3. BUSCO scores of transcriptome assemblies

Table S4. Values from Gene Concordance (gCF) and Site Concordance (sCF) analyses

Table S5. Sample and collection data for mitochondrial data

I. Species tree phylogenetic analyses of new transcriptomic data

Figure S1. Duplication of Figure 1 for convenient comparison to additional analyses in this supplement. Species phylogeny inferred using multi-species-coalescent, employed with ASTRAL-PRO (Zhang et al. 2020) with 8485 gene trees, each of which included both orthologs and paralogs. We calculated each gene tree using fasttree 2.1.10 (Price et al. 2010) assuming a JTT+CAT model. Above the tree, we also labeled non-cypridinid Outgroups (green), and Cypridinidinae (Orange). We herein suggest a name for the bioluminescent Cypridinidinae to be Tribe Luminini (after the Greek lumen for light + -ini = typical zoological tribe suffix) and a name for the clade containing signaling cypridinids to be Sub-Tribe Luxorina (lux = light + uxoriae ~ = courtship + -ina = typical zoological subtribe suffix). Locality abbreviations for collecting sites of species are above each tip as follows: AU = Australia, BZ=Belize, CA=California, USA, CU=Curacao, JA= Jamaica, JP=Japan, PA=Panama, PP=Previously Published, PR = Puerto Rico, and RO=Roatan, Honduras (see Table S1 for specific localities). Above locality names are abbreviations for species, which are expanded in Fig. S2.

Figure S2. Multi-species coalescent species tree (equivalent to Figs 1, S1) with full species names rather than abbreviations. Numbers at nodes are posterior probability values. See Figs 1 and S1 for detailed methods.

Table S1. Specimen collection and transcriptome sequencing information

Taxon	Country	Lat.	Long.	Voucher Museum	Voucher Accession	Transcriptome Accession	Transcriptome file name (local)	Library Prep Kit	Illumina Vers.	Sequencing Facility
<i>Alternochelata lizardensis</i>	Australia	-14.6689	145.4594	AMS	P.92342-4	SRX3829269	TOCC003A	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Chelicopia lorica</i>	Australia	-14.6828	145.4481	AMS	P.92345-8	SRR17097280	TOCC003B	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Cypridina sp</i>	Australia			AMS	P.92467	SRR17097274	TOCC004G	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Euphilomedes sp</i>	Australia			AMS	P.92379-80	SRR17097276	TOCC004C	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Harbansus slatteryi</i>	Australia	-14.6830	145.4495	AMS	P.92355-61	SRR17097279	TOCC003F	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Paradoloria sp</i>	Australia			AMS	P.92314-5	SRR17097273	TOCC004H	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Paravargula sp</i>	Australia			AMS	P.92316-7	SRR17097278	TOCC003G	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Pterocypridina spLIRS</i>	Australia			AMS	P.92319	SRR17097271	TOCC004I	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Vargula sp</i>	Australia			AMS	P.92349	SRR17097275	TOCC004F	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Kornickeria hastingsi carrie-bowae</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10860879	Korn_hast_c	Prepared at Novogene	Novo-gene	Novogene
<i>Kornickeria hastingsi carrie-bowae</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10860878	Kornickeria_hastingsii_carrie-bowae_Rep2	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	Functional Genomics Lab
<i>Maristella BZ SVU</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	USNM 1659658	SRR10811643	Sample_TOCC001C_index3	RNA TruSeq V2	v3 PE	Functional Genomics Lab
<i>Maristella BZ SVU</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	USNM 1659658	SRR10811644	B_SVU	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella BZ SVD</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	USNM 1659659	SRR10860875	Maristella_SVD	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella BZ SVD</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	USNM 1659659	SRR10860874	Maristella_SVD_Rep2	RNA TruSeq v2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Maristella BZ VAD</i>	Belize	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659657	SRR17097283	BZ-VAD2_S4	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella BZ VAD</i>	Belize	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659657	SRR17097272	BZ-VAD_S4	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella BZ VAD</i>	Belize	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659657	SRR17097270	BZVAD	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella chicoi</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10811640	B_MSH	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella chicoi</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10811639	BzMSH	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	Functional Genomics Lab
<i>Photeros annecohenae</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10860880	Gruber_Pannecohenae	RNA TruSeq v3	v3 PE	New York Genome Center
<i>Photeros morini</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10860877	B_Pmorin	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Photeros morini</i>	Belize	16.8116	-88.0824	NMNH	No voucher	SRR10860876	Sample_TOCC001B_index2	RNA TruSeq V2	v3 PE	Functional Genomics Lab
<i>Skogsbergia sp BZG</i>	Belize	16.7470	-87.8097	No voucher	No voucher	SRR17097268	GlovSkogs	RNA TruSeq V2	v3 PE	BGI
<i>Kornickeria CU SDF</i>	Curacao	12.1094	-68.9545	SBMNH	SBMNH 658185	SRR17097269	CURA	Prepared at Novogene	Novo-gene	Novogene
<i>Kornickeria RO CMU</i>	Honduras	16.3581	-86.4329	NMNH	USNM 1659663	SRR17097291	R-CMU_S63_L008	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center

<i>Kornickeria RO CMU</i>	Honduras	16.3581	-86.4329	NMNH	USNM 1659663	SRR17097292	R-CMU_S5	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO AG</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659662	SRR10811636	EETO030418-RO_AG	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	UCSB-BNL
<i>Maristella RO DU</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659667	SRR17097289	R-DU_S60	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO DU</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659667	SRR17097290	R-DU_S3	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO DU</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659667	SRR17097284	R2016DU	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO IR</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659665	SRR12672004	R-IR_S66_L008	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO ODH</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659661	SRR12672003	R_ODH	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella RO ODH</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659661	SRR17097288	R-OHD_S65_L008	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO RD</i>	Honduras	16.3581	-86.4329	NMNH	USNM 1659660	SRR17097285	R-RD2_S1	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO RD</i>	Honduras	16.3581	-86.4329	NMNH	USNM 1659660	SRR17097287	R-RD_S1	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella RO RD</i>	Honduras	16.3581	-86.4329	NMNH	USNM 1659660	SRR17097287	R-RD_S59	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Photeros RO GPH</i>	Honduras	16.4027	-86.4090	NMNH	USNM 1659666	SRR17097293	R_GPH	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	UCSB-BNL
<i>Photeros RO GPH</i>	Honduras	16.4027	-86.4090	NMNH	USNM 1659666	SRR17097282	RO2015GPH	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Photeros RO WLU</i>	Honduras	16.8065	-88.0790	NMNH	USNM 1659664	SRR10811635	EETO030418-RO_WLU	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	UCSB-BNL
<i>Jimmorinia gunnari</i>	Jamaica	18.4700	-77.4100	NMNH	No voucher	SRR17097315	J_JimGun-43942958	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	UCSB-BNL
<i>Jimmorinia gunnari</i>	Jamaica	18.4700	-77.4100	NMNH	No voucher	SRR17097306	JAM_JIMMOR	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella JA AU</i>	Jamaica	18.4723	-77.4095	NMNH	USNM 1659654	SRR17097312	J-AU_S56_L007	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA LSZZ</i>	Jamaica	18.4715	-77.4148	NMNH	USNM 1659653	SRR17097300	LSZZ_S3	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA LSZZ</i>	Jamaica	18.4715	-77.4148	NMNH	USNM 1659653	SRR17097304	JAM_LSZZ	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA OBD</i>	Jamaica	18.4723	-77.4095	NMNH	No voucher	SRR17097310	J-OBD_S52	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA OBD</i>	Jamaica	18.4723	-77.4095	NMNH	No voucher	SRR17097314	J_OBD	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella JA SVD</i>	Jamaica	18.4802	-77.4460	NMNH	USNM 1659651	SRR17097313	J_SVD	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Maristella JA SVD</i>	Jamaica	18.4802	-77.4460	NMNH	USNM 1659651	SRR17097309	J-SVD_S53	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA VAD</i>	Jamaica	18.4737	-77.4169	NMNH	USNM 1659652	SRR10811642	J-VAD_S55	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA VAD</i>	Jamaica	18.4737	-77.4169	NMNH	USNM 1659652	SRR10811641	J_VAD-43931095	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	UCSB-BNL

<i>Maristella JA WLU</i>	Jamaica	18.4723	-77.4095	NMNH	USNM 1659647	SRR17097308	J-WLU_S67_L008	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Maristella JA WTF</i>	Jamaica	18.4733	-77.4128	NMNH	USNM 1659655	SRR17097307	J-WTF_S54_L007	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Photeros jamescasei</i>	Jamaica	18.4737	-77.4169	NMNH	USNM 1659648	SRR17097311	J-Jamescasei2_S5	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Photeros jamescasei</i>	Jamaica	18.4737	-77.4169	NMNH	USNM 1659648	SRR17097267	J_Jamescasei-43938115	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	UCSB-BNL
<i>Photeros mcelroyi</i>	Jamaica	18.4751	-77.4055	NMNH	USNM 1659650	SRR10811638	J-MacElroyi_S2	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Photeros mcelroyi</i>	Jamaica	18.4751	-77.4055	NMNH	USNM 1659650	SRR10811637	J-MacElroyi2_S2	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Photeros mcelroyi</i>	Jamaica	18.4751	-77.4055	NMNH	USNM 1659650	SRR10811645	JMACELROY	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Cypridinodes sp</i>	Japan	34.6737	138.9743	SBMNH	SBMNH 658174	-	jpcyp2b	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Melavargula japonica</i>	Japan	34.6737	138.9743	SBMNH	SBMNH 658182	SRR17097303	Jp_Melavar22	NEBNext® Ultra™ RNA	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Paravargula maculosa</i>	Japan	34.6737	138.9743	SBMNH	SBMNH 658180	SRR17097305	3_S8_L001	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Paravargula maculosa</i>	Japan	34.6737	138.9743	SBMNH	SBMNH 658180	SRR17097294	3-2_S9_L001	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Vargula hilgendorffii</i>	Japan			No voucher	No voucher	SRR17097277	TOCC003H	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Vargula hilgendorffii 2</i>	Japan			No voucher	No voucher	SRR17097317	1_S6	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>Vargula hilgendorffii 2</i>	Japan			No voucher	No voucher	SRR17097316	1-2_S7	RNA TruSeq V3	v3 PE	UC Davis Genome Center
<i>PA MFU</i>	Panama	9.3313	-82.2533	NHNM	No voucher	SRR17097296	PMMFU	Prepared at Novogene	Novo-gene	Novogene
<i>Photeros PA EGD</i>	Panama	9.3326	-82.2539	SBMNH	SBMNH 658179	SRR17097299	Panama_Photeros_EGD__EGD__Niko	Prepared at Novogene	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Photeros PA NOL</i>	Panama	9.3546	-82.2587	SBMNH	SBMNH 658177	SRR17097298	Panama_Photeros_NOL__NOL__Niko	Prepared at Novogene	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Photeros PA SFM</i>	Panama	9.3327	-82.2536	SBMNH	SBMNH 658201	SRR17097297	Panama_Photeros_SFM__SFM__Niko	Prepared at Novogene	v3 PE	Novogene
<i>Skogsbergia sp PA</i>	Panama	9.3300	-82.2500		No voucher	SRR17097295	PSKOG	Prepared at Novogene	Novo-gene	Novogene
<i>Gigantocypris sp</i>	USA				No voucher	SRR17097301	L4_Gigantocypris_MBARI	RNA TruSeq V2	v3 PE	BGI
<i>Vargula tsujii</i>	USA	33.4451	-118.4845	SBMNH	SBMNH 660969	SRR21201581	TOCC0031	RNA TruSeq V2	v2 PE	BGI
<i>Cylindroleberidinae</i>	Belize	16.8030	-88.0810	MCZ	MCZ IZ 74242	SRR4113495				
<i>Darwinula stevensoni</i>	Belgium	Unknown		Unknown	Unknown	ENA PRJEB38362				

Table S2. Carapace measurements

Species Designation	Collector	Meas. by	Lat.	Long.	N (len/eye/keel)	Len (mm)	Min. Len	Max. Len	Height (mm)	Min. Height	Max. Height	Eye (mm)	Min. Eye	Max. Eye	Keel (mm)	Min. Keel	Max. Keel	L/H
<i>Kornickeria CU SDF</i>	JAG/THO		12.1094	-68.9545														
<i>Kornickeria hastingsi carriebowie</i>	GAG/JGM	GAG	16.8116	-88.0824	37/15/15	1.80	1.72	1.86	1.01	0.96	1.06	0.25	0.22	0.28	0.12	0.10	0.12	1.774
<i>Kornickeria RO CMU</i>	GAG/EAE	GAG	16.3581	-86.4329	67/28/28	1.77	1.72	1.86	1.00	0.96	1.05	0.20	0.16	0.25	0.12	0.08	0.18	1.775
<i>Maristella BZ SVD</i>	GAG/JGM	GAG	16.8116	-88.0824	19/13/13	1.76	1.68	1.86	1.06	0.98	1.10	0.18	0.16	0.20	0.07	0.06	0.10	1.666
<i>Maristella BZ SVU</i>	GAG/JGM	GAG	16.8116	-88.0824	71/15/15	2.17	2.06	2.28	1.31	1.22	1.42	0.27	0.24	0.36	0.17	0.14	0.22	1.664
<i>Maristella BZ VAD</i>	GAG/EAE	GAG	16.8065	-88.0790	35/20/20	1.87	1.78	1.93	1.11	1.05	1.15	0.23	0.20	0.28	0.11	0.10	0.13	1.690
<i>Maristella chicoi</i>	GAG/JGM	GAG	16.8116	-88.0824	68/32/32	1.62	1.56	1.70	0.96	0.92	1.00	0.22	0.16	0.26	0.07	0.04	0.08	1.686
<i>Maristella JA AU</i>	GAG/JPF	GAG	18.4723	-77.4095	34/34/34	2.17	2.10	2.23	1.23	1.15	1.28	0.25	0.20	0.28	0.12	0.10	0.15	1.772
<i>Maristella JA LSZZ</i>	NMH/JGM/ TJR	GAG	18.4715	-77.4148	18/18/18	1.70	1.63	1.75	1.03	1.00	1.05	0.19	0.18	0.20	0.10	0.08	0.13	1.650
<i>Maristella JA OBD</i>	GAG/TJR/ JGM	GAG	18.4723	-77.4095	42/27/27	1.79	1.75	1.85	1.06	1.00	1.10	0.21	0.20	0.25	0.08	0.08	0.13	1.692
<i>Maristella JA SVD</i>	GAG/JPF/ NMH	GAG	18.4802	-77.4460	59/49/49	1.95	1.88	2.03	1.15	1.10	1.20	0.22	0.20	0.25	0.09	0.08	0.10	1.700
<i>Maristella JA VAD</i>	TJR/JPF/ JGM	GAG	18.4737	-77.4169	47/28/28	2.18	2.08	2.25	1.21	1.15	1.25	0.23	0.18	0.25	0.11	0.10	0.15	1.807
<i>Maristella JA WLU</i>	TJR/GAG/ NMH/JPF	GAG	18.4723	-77.4095	55/26/26	1.92	1.88	1.98	1.13	1.10	1.20	0.22	0.20	0.25	0.11	0.10	0.13	1.694
<i>Maristella JA WTF</i>	GAG	GAG	18.4733	-77.4128	12/12/12	1.89	1.83	1.95	1.13	1.08	1.18	0.22	0.20	0.23	0.10	0.10	0.13	1.670
<i>Maristella RO AG</i>	GAG/EAE	GAG	16.8065	-88.0790	31/31/31	2.29	2.16	2.40	1.39	1.30	1.43	0.22	0.20	0.25	0.17	0.13	0.20	1.649
<i>Maristella RO DU</i>	GAG/JGM/ EAE	GAG	16.8065	-88.0790	54/34/32	1.63	1.58	1.73	0.98	0.94	1.05	0.21	0.18	0.28	0.09	0.06	0.10	1.663
<i>Maristella RO IR</i>	GAG/NMH	GAG	16.8065	-88.0790	52/30/30	2.28	2.22	2.38	1.39	1.35	1.44	0.23	0.20	0.25	0.15	0.12	0.18	1.646
<i>Maristella RO ODH</i>	GAG/JGM	GAG	16.8065	-88.0790	40/20/20	1.69	1.64	1.76	0.99	0.96	1.04	0.20	0.16	0.22	0.08	0.06	0.10	1.711
<i>Maristella RO RD</i>	JGM/NMH	GAG	16.3581	-86.4329	51/31/31	1.64	1.58	1.70	0.98	0.94	1.03	0.18	0.14	0.23	0.08	0.06	0.10	1.670
<i>PA MFU</i>	JGM	GAG	9.3313	-82.2533	30/20/20	1.66	1.58	1.70	1.00	0.95	1.05	0.19	0.18	0.20	0.08	0.08	0.10	1.654
<i>Photeros annecohenae</i>	GAG/JGM	JGM	16.8116	-88.0824	121/15/15	1.62	1.50	1.70	1.02	0.96	1.08	0.22	0.18	0.26	0.12	0.08	0.16	1.591
<i>Photeros jamescasei</i>	JPF/GAG/ JGM	GAG	18.4737	-77.4169	36/30/30	2.07	1.98	2.13	1.31	1.23	1.35	0.27	0.25	0.30	0.14	0.10	0.15	1.576
<i>Photeros mcelroyi</i>	NMH/GAG/ JGM	GAG	18.4751	-77.4055	41/35/35	1.92	1.85	2.00	1.22	1.18	1.25	0.27	0.23	0.30	0.13	0.10	0.18	1.576
<i>Photeros morini</i>	GAG/JGM	GAG	16.8116	-88.0824	45/15/15	2.06	1.94	2.14	1.28	1.20	1.36	0.37	0.34	0.40	0.11	0.08	0.12	1.604
<i>Photeros PA EGD</i>	NMH/JGM	GAG	9.3326	-82.2539	18/16/16	1.63	1.58	1.65	1.04	1.03	1.08	0.18	0.18	0.20	0.10	0.08	0.13	1.557
<i>Photeros PA NOL</i>	THO, NMH	THO	9.3546	-82.2587	14/14/14	1.63	1.55	1.67	1.04	1.01	1.07	0.21	0.19	0.25	0.10	0.08	0.13	1.567
<i>Photeros PA SFM</i>	NMH/JGM	GAG/ EAE	9.3327	-82.2536	60/50/50	1.70	1.63	1.78	1.08	1.03	1.13	0.19	0.16	0.23	0.09	0.05	0.12	1.581
<i>Photeros RO GPH</i>	GAG	GAG	16.4027	-86.4090	40/20/20	1.68	1.60	1.74	1.04	1.00	1.08	0.23	0.22	0.26	0.09	0.08	0.10	1.621
<i>Photeros RO WLU</i>	GAG/JGM/ NMH	GAG	16.8065	-88.0790	53/31/31	1.98	1.82	2.17	1.22	1.10	1.43	0.24	0.20	0.30	0.13	0.10	0.17	1.619

Table S3. Metrics of transcriptome completeness

Species	BUSCO v3 Complete (Max 1066 arth_db9)	Number of Contigs	N50	Transdecoder.v3 Complete ORFs
<i>Alternochelata lizardensis</i>	316	8573	367	1443
<i>Chelicopia lorica</i>	436	111956	506	2736
<i>Cylindroleberidinae</i>	755	833810	389	15389
<i>Cypridina sp</i>	758	232667	595	6158
<i>Cypridinodes sp</i>	622	220069	430	3186
<i>Darwinula stevensoni</i>	928	62117	56422	14612
<i>Euphilomedes sp</i>	559	67419	444	5676
<i>Gigantocypris sp</i>	458	60294	545	3050
<i>Harbansus slatteryi</i>	623	112493	649	3958
<i>Jimmorinia gunnari</i>	47	25397	284	145
<i>Kornickeria CU SDF</i>	525	123953	391	2877
<i>Kornickeria hastingsi carriebowae</i>	675	131518	520	5040
<i>Kornickeria RO CMU</i>	914	459761	441	12132
<i>Maristella BZ SVD</i>	465	97454	540	3541
<i>Maristella BZ SVU</i>	318	96641	408	1507
<i>Maristella BZ VAD</i>	573	353073	368	4996
<i>Maristella chicoi</i>	344	166512	406	23425
<i>Maristella JA AU</i>	781	223647	522	7777
<i>Maristella JA LSZZ</i>	355	308104	326	2534
<i>Maristella JA OBD</i>	738	164684	580	8174
<i>Maristella JA SVD</i>	764	225704	516	7966
<i>Maristella JA VAD</i>	675	307747	386	6187
<i>Maristella JA WLU</i>	896	273365	608	12250
<i>Maristella JA WTF</i>	712	172775	561	7629
<i>Maristella RO AG</i>	861	578384	396	10812
<i>Maristella RO DU</i>	871	326035	430	7465
<i>Maristella RO IR</i>	584	169966	469	4860
<i>Maristella RO ODH</i>	803	202233	577	8765
<i>Maristella RO RD</i>	836	305801	486	8995
<i>Melavargula japonica</i>	96	66028	314	305
<i>PA MFU</i>	454	110867	400	3022
<i>Paradoloria sp</i>	755	168668	649	6668
<i>Paravargula maculosa</i>	251	52293	431	1344
<i>Paravargula sp</i>	540	124555	650	3086
<i>Photeros annecohenae</i>	843	330459	647	13707
<i>Photeros jamescasei</i>	6	5044	254	32
<i>Photeros mcelroyi</i>	148	197717	304	935
<i>Photeros morini</i>	197	7576	262	985
<i>Photeros PA EGD</i>	662	178943	697	11910
<i>Photeros PA NOL</i>	710	195227	683	9482
<i>Photeros PA SFM</i>	746	188191	742	11538
<i>Photeros RO GPH</i>	455	385152	365	4255
<i>Photeros RO WLU</i>	860	395655	462	10779
<i>Pterocypridina spLIRS</i>	514	145874	576	3926
<i>Skogsbergia sp BZG</i>	122	59380	365	8101
<i>Skogsbergia sp PA</i>	676	152911	402	3832
<i>Vargula hilgendorfi</i>	336	51891	561	1184
<i>Vargula hilgendorfi sp 2</i>	292	45009	400	7576
<i>Vargula sp</i>	268	51872	488	970
<i>Vargula tsujii</i>	607	122949	573	4317

Figure S3. Concatenated analyses of 2675 orthologs determined with Orthofinder 2.5.2 and Phylopypruner 0.9.7 using Maximum Likelihood implemented in IQ-TREE v2.0.3, with additional options for -bnni and -alrt (set to 1000) for 1000 bootstrap replicates.

Figure S4 - Gene concordance analysis of 2675 gene families containing only orthologs, determined with Orthofinder 2.5.2 and Phylopypruner 0.9.7, implemented in IQ-TREE v2.0.3 with an additional option set (--scf 100).

Table S4. Values from Gene Concordance (gCF) and Site Concordance (sCF) analyses implemented in IQ-TREE using orthofinder/phylopruner orthologs.

ID	gCF	gCF_N	gDF1	gDF1_N	gDF2	gDF2_N	gDFP	gDFP_N	gN	sCF	sCF_N	sDF1	sDF1_N	sDF2	sDF2_N	sN	Bootstrap
51	47.25	686	11.5	167	9.85	143	31.4	456	1452	68.1	437.6	18.06	96.15	13.84	89.84	623.59	100/100
52	36.96	272	7.74	57	8.29	61	47.01	346	736	80.12	633.09	11.01	76.07	8.87	59.43	768.59	100/100
53	23.85	171	6.28	45	3.63	26	66.25	475	717	28.37	206.13	60.17	466.27	11.47	81.54	753.94	100/100
54	8.82	149	6.1	103	5.74	97	79.34	1340	1689	30.24	219.95	41.2	305	28.56	206.12	731.07	96.6/95
55	12.66	222	6.45	113	4.28	75	76.61	1343	1753	45.1	298.65	28.61	167.75	26.29	157.63	624.03	100/100
56	52.32	688	3.27	43	2.51	33	41.9	551	1315	67.39	509.67	16.81	92.63	15.79	92.88	695.18	100/100
57	69.6	893	5.53	71	5.46	70	19.41	249	1283	87.75	778.13	4.15	31.1	8.11	55.96	865.19	100/100
58	36.74	377	5.07	52	5.17	53	53.02	544	1026	60.84	418.38	20.13	102.94	19.03	116.47	637.79	100/100
59	13.37	271	5.38	109	6.36	129	74.89	1518	2027	33.92	234.39	27.83	178.07	38.25	260.09	672.55	100/100
60	53.03	1101	2.07	43	1.97	41	42.92	891	2076	70.35	826.21	18.86	162.84	10.79	114.49	1103.54	100/100
61	71.29	899	3.01	38	3.81	48	21.89	276	1261	75.96	782.18	13.35	105.62	10.69	102.14	989.94	100/100
62	75.51	771	7.35	75	6.66	68	10.48	107	1021	83.42	733.13	10.67	72.81	5.91	45.26	851.2	100/100
63M	57.34	1226	3.23	69	5.99	128	33.44	715	2138	62.86	1244.82	14.55	264.72	22.59	374.41	1883.95	100/100
64	61.33	1388	1.68	38	1.1	25	35.88	812	2263	63.21	914.88	20.31	225.14	16.48	208.19	1348.21	100/100
65P	83.29	1730	0.19	4	0.29	6	16.23	337	2077	92.32	1334.67	3.41	37.79	4.27	43.89	1416.35	100/100
66	27.78	474	11.66	199	12.25	209	48.3	824	1706	61.94	143.51	20.49	64	17.57	51.97	259.48	100/100
67	28.04	496	12.04	213	11.93	211	47.99	849	1769	58.04	352.61	18.95	117.61	23.01	134.46	604.68	100/100
68	22.62	307	19.68	267	18.2	247	39.5	536	1357	29.75	129.02	41.42	167.65	28.84	115.8	412.47	60.5/66
69	10.42	115	13.32	147	26.09	288	50.18	554	1104	22.53	51.82	23.56	46.64	52.92	80.89	179.35	72.8/72
70	15.08	68	9.09	41	9.76	44	66.08	298	451	39.81	45.36	26.78	30.49	30.41	39.7	115.55	99.9/100
71	49.38	79	8.13	13	5	8	37.5	60	160	46.63	24.41	25.26	25.47	26.11	11.04	60.92	99.9/76
72	0	0	27.27	3	18.18	2	54.55	6	11	27.08	0.48	21.26	0.53	31.66	0.48	1.49	69.1/36
73	24.68	609	14.59	360	18.4	454	42.34	1045	2468	33.3	455.28	31.18	405.91	34.52	432.8	1293.99	100/100
74K	65.89	1219	4.11	76	4.92	91	25.08	464	1850	55.17	1418.75	21.57	542.85	23.26	582.56	2544.16	100/100
75	93.48	1519	1.29	21	1.11	18	4.12	67	1625	97.05	5954	1.57	77.16	1.38	72.79	6103.95	100/100
76*	49.78	1111	3.54	79	4.44	99	42.25	943	2232	53.45	829.73	22.42	329.9	24.12	346.2	1505.83	100/100
77**	45.29	77	10	17	5.29	9	39.41	67	170	53.88	77.6	22.06	32.33	23.06	30.33	140.26	100/100
78	41.44	46	6.31	7	7.21	8	45.05	50	111	46.15	62.92	26.86	36.97	26.99	35.81	135.7	100/100
79	30	261	7.24	63	12.64	110	50.11	436	870	39.49	690.88	30.02	510.42	30.49	513.47	1714.77	100/100
80	18.62	213	20.1	230	16.96	194	44.32	507	1144	35.56	403.29	34.21	384.59	30.23	338.2	1126.08	100/100
81	60.45	405	3.43	23	3.13	21	32.99	221	670	69.94	394.51	15.15	87.39	14.91	87.72	569.62	100/100
82	29.42	188	10.33	66	27.7	177	32.55	208	639	39.95	187.66	22.95	102.36	36.1	155.5	445.52	100/95
83	64.5	674	8.8	92	8.71	91	17.99	188	1045	55.05	675.37	23.63	276.34	21.33	264.77	1216.48	100/100
84	90.07	689	3.4	26	2.48	19	4.05	31	765	94.77	1690.34	2.92	52.45	2.31	41.06	1783.85	100/100
85	27.91	96	19.19	66	14.53	50	38.37	132	344	43.08	150.57	33.56	116.66	23.36	79.84	347.07	99.8/93
86	45.28	72	10.06	16	10.69	17	33.96	54	159	62.57	134.38	22.18	47.28	15.24	32.71	214.37	100/100
87	52.11	420	4.09	33	5.33	43	38.46	310	806	60.73	537.48	19.57	176.2	19.7	175.72	889.4	100/100
88	35.05	211	19.1	115	20.1	121	25.75	155	602	32.96	399.42	30.67	375.65	36.37	422.32	1197.39	100/100
89	65.6	328	6.4	32	9.2	46	18.8	94	500	50.98	651.46	24.23	302.81	24.79	311.04	1265.31	100/100
90	63.43	137	7.41	16	17.59	38	11.57	25	216	47.43	301.43	22.26	142.96	30.3	189.86	634.25	100/100
91	89.59	198	5.88	13	0.9	2	3.62	8	221	93.67	1015.96	3.64	38.89	2.69	30.24	1085.09	100/100
92	64.37	952	8.45	125	5.61	83	21.57	319	1479	52.98	670.62	26.98	329.59	20.04	244.25	1244.46	100/100
93	73.25	638	8.73	76	8.04	70	9.99	87	871	69.43	992.62	15.44	219.32	15.13	213.95	1425.89	100/100
94	90.05	516	2.62	15	2.27	13	5.06	29	573	97.45	1122.64	1.78	19.05	0.77	7.88	1149.57	100/100
95Z	63.41	792	7.53	94	9.37	117	19.7	246	1249	56.31	899.2	20.12	311.28	23.57	355.88	1566.36	100/100
96	44.83	507	5.13	58	3.98	45	46.07	521	1131	64.44	328.21	19.8	91.29	15.76	74.85	494.35	100/100
97	57.83	569	7.72	76	7.32	72	27.13	267	984	78.84	395.33	10.56	47.44	10.6	43.15	485.92	100/100

*Node 76 is the common ancestor of species with courtship signaling.

**Node 77 is the common ancestor of species with bioluminescence.

P Node 65 is the common ancestor of *Photeros*

K Node 74 is the common ancestor of *Kornickeria*

M Node 63 is the common ancestor of *Maristella*

Z Node 95 is the common ancestor of Z-group

II. Bayesian relaxed molecular clock analyses of divergence times

Figure S5. Relaxed molecular clock analysis. Figure 2 copied for more convenient comparison with Fig. S9. **A.** We used a Bayesian relaxed molecular clock approach, implemented in MrBayes (Ronquist and Huelsenbeck 2003) with 15 orthologs selected using sortadate (Smith, Brown, and Walker 2018). We used two fossil constraints: Mydocopida, with offset exponential prior with a minimum of 448.8 MY and maximum of 509 MY and Ostracoda with a uniform prior between 443.8 and 509 MY (Oakley et al. 2013; Wolfe et al. 2016). We used the Independent Gamma Rate (IGR) model in MrBayes, (Lepage et al. 2007; Chi Zhang 2016) with a prior of $\exp(10)$. We assumed a lognormal distribution with a mean of 0.001 and standard deviation of 0.0007 for the rate prior. We assumed fixed-rate amino acid models with `aamodelpr=mixed`. We ran 500K steps of Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) in two chains, using a starting phylogeny based on parsimony. **B.** Results of time-tree stochastic character mapping (ttscm) estimates origin of bioluminescence to be 267 MYA because that is the median age of character state transitions to bioluminescence. **C.** Similarly, ttscm estimates the origin of luminous courtship to be 213 MYA.

Figure S6. Relaxed molecular clock analysis as in S8 showing 95% Highest Posterior Densities at each node.

Figure S7. Sensitivity analysis of divergence time estimates using subsets of genes with Sortdate. We compared results from 15 (x-axis), 20, 25 and 30 (y-axis) genes, keeping all other parameters constant.

Figure S8. Posterior probability values of nodal support from Bayesian analysis using 15 genes selected with sortdate.

Table S5. Accession, sample, and collection data for mitochondrial data.

Species (Fig S11)	Fig. 3	Locale	12S Accession	16S Accession	COI Accession	Source	Synonymous sample names	Location	Collector	Year
Cylindroleberidinae	(not shown)	PP	N/A	DN177767_c165_g1_i1	N/A	Schwentner et al (2018)				
<i>Cypridinodes_sp</i>	Cypsp	PP	N/A	AY624732.1	N/A					
<i>Gigantocypris_CA_sp</i>	Gigsp	CA	OL828721	OL828505	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Gigantocypris_sp	Santa Barbara, CA	S. Haddock	unknown
<i>Gigantocypris_CA_sp</i>	Gigsp	PP	N/A	N/A	KP745264.1	Nigro et al (2016)	Gigantocypris_muelleri			
<i>Paradoloria_pellucida</i>	Ppel	PP	N/A	AY624734.1	N/A	Wakayama and Abe (2006)				
<i>Paravargula_maculosa</i>	Pmac	AU	DN5047_c0_g1_i1	N/A	DN6496_c0_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)	BothPara_w			
<i>Heterodesmus_adamsii</i>	Hada	PP	N/A	MH784581.1	MH815006.1	Pham et al (2020)				
<i>Skogsbergia_BZ_sp</i>	Skobz	BZ	DN16047_c0_g2	N/A	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)	GlovSkog			
<i>Paradoloria_AU_sp</i>	Prvsp	AU	DN39598_c1_g2_i1	N/A	DN32407_c0_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)	FatWhiteEye			
<i>Pterocypridina_AU_spLIRS</i>	Ptesp	AU	DN45931_c1_g6_i7	N/A	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)	WhiteVanessa			
<i>Skogsbergia_lernerii</i>	Sler	BA	OL828722	OL828506	OL810011	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Lernerii2017B	Bimini Id., Bahamas	E. Torres, V. Gonzalez	unknown
<i>Skogsbergia_crenulata</i>	Scre	VI	N/A	OL828507	OL810012	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	crenulataUSVI01	St. Thomas, US Virgin Islands	E. Torres	unknown
<i>Paradoloria_sp</i>	Parsp	AU	OL828723	OL828508	OL810013	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Paradoloria_sp. VG	Jervis Bay, NSW, Australia	A. Parker	unknown
<i>Melavargula_sp</i>	Melsp		N/A	OL828509	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)		Okinawa, Japan	M. Grygier	unknown
<i>Melavargula_japonica</i>	Mjap	JP	N/A	AY624733.1	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Vargula_norvegica</i>	Vnor	AT	OL828724	OL828510	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Vnorvegica	deep sea Atlantic sampling	A. Heger	unknown
<i>Vargula_karamu</i>	Vkar	AU	OL828725	OL828511	OL810014	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Vargula_karamu = VarAP8	Botany Bay, NSW, Australia	A. Parker	unknown
<i>Sheina_orri</i>	Sorr	AU	N/A	OL828512	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Sheina_sp	Lizard Id., Australia	A. Parker	unknown
<i>Jimmorinia</i>	Jim	VI	OL828726	OL828513	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Jimmorinia	St. Thomas, US Virgin Islands	E. Torres	unknown
<i>Vargula_tubulata</i>	Vtub	AU	N/A	OL828514	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Vtubulata	Jervis Bay, NSW, Australia	A. Parker	unknown
<i>Vargula_hilgendorffii</i>	Vhil	JP	NC_005306.1	NC_005306.1	NC_005306.1	Ogoh and Ohmiya (2004) mt genome	Vargula hilgendorffii			
<i>Vargula_hilgendorffii_shimoda</i>	Vhils	JP	N/A	N/A	DN8252_c1_g4_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Cypridina_dentata</i>	Cden	PP	NC_042792.1	NC_042792.1	NC_042792.1	Wang et al (2019) mt genome				
<i>Cypridina_AU_spVG</i>	Cyp-spVG	AU	OL828727	OL828515	OL810015	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Cypridina_sp = Cyp2A	Palm Beach, NSW, Australia	A. Parker	unknown

Table S5 (continued). Sample and collection data for mitochondrial data

Species (Fig S11)	Fig. 3	Locale	12S Accession	16S Accession	CO1 Accession	Source	Synonymous sample names	Location	Collector	Year
<i>Cypridina_noctiluca</i>	Cnoc	JP	N/A	AY624731.1	N/A	Wakayama and Abe (2006)				
<i>Kornickeria_CU_SDF</i>	SDF	CU	DN58992_c0_g2_i1	N/A	DN71800_c56_g6_i2	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Kornickeria_FL_GU</i>	GU	FL	OL828728	OL828516	OL810016	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	KornGU = KornGUB	Looe Key, Florida	E. Torres and J. Morin	1992
<i>Kornickeria_marleyi</i>	Kmar	JA	OL828729	OL828517	OL810017	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Kornmarleyi = Mar30B	Discovery Bay, Jamaica	P. Edmunds	unknown
<i>Kornickeria_hastingsi</i>	Khas	BZ	OL828730	OL828518	OL810018	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	KhastingsiBZ0604D = BZ0706.04C	Carrie Bow Caye, Belize	E. Torres and A. Cohen	unknown
<i>Kornickeria_RO_CMU</i>	CMU	RO	N/A	DN224514_c3_g2_i2	DN224514_c3_g2_i2	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Photeros_morini</i>	Pmor	BZ	DN109008_c0_g1_i2	N/A	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	PVFF = BZ1024A	Carrie Bow Caye, Belize	E. Torres and A. Cohen	unknown
<i>Photeros_graminicola</i>	Pgra	PA	OL828731	OL828519	OL810019	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Pgraminicola = GRAMB	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Photeros_FL_WLOU</i>	WLOU	FL	OL828732	OL828520	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	PWLOU = WlousA	Looe Key, Florida	E. Torres and J. Morin	1992
<i>Photeros_FL_QF</i>	QF	FL	OL828733	OL828521	OL810020	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	PQF = QFA	Looe Key, Florida	E. Torres and J. Morin	1992
<i>Photeros_shulmanae</i>	Pshu	PA	N/A	OL828522	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	Pshulmanae = Pshul	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Photeros_annecohenae</i>	Pann	BZ	DN86176_c0_g3_i1	N/A	N/A	Hensley et al 2020 Transcriptome	Gruber_Pannecohenae			
<i>Photeros_PA_SFM</i>	SFM	PA	DN21_c0_g2_i2	DN21_c0_g2_i2	DN21_c0_g2_i2	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Photeros_PA_EGD</i>	EGD	PA	DN488_c0_g2_i2	N/A	DN488_c0_g2_i2	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Photeros_PA_NOL</i>	NOL	PA	DN760_c0_g1_i10	DN760_c0_g1_i10	DN760_c0_g1_i10	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Vargula_tsujii</i>	Vtsu	CA	NC_039175.1	NC_039175.1	NC_039175.1	Goodheart et al (2020) mt genome				
<i>Vargula_PA_MFU</i>	MFU	PA	DN9711_c0_g1_i1	N/A	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Vargula_mizonomma</i>	Vmiz	PA	OL828734	OL828523	OL810021	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	ZGRPmizonomma = VMizoCD	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Vargula_kuna</i>	Vkun	PA	OL828735	OL828524	N/A	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	kuna1B = Kuna934A	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Maristella_chicoi</i>	Mchi	BZ	N/A	N/A	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_JA_LSZZ</i>	LSZZ	JA	DN182361_c2_g1_i5	N/A	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_JA_AU</i>	AU	AU	DN57492_c0_g2_i1	N/A	DN56818_c0_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_JA_VAD</i>	JVAD	JA	N/A	N/A	DN94762_c1_g2_i2	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_BZ_VAD</i>	BVAD	BZ	DN209300_c0_g3_i2	DN209300_c0_g3_i2	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)				

Table S5 (continued). Sample and collection data for mitochondrial data

Species (Fig S11)	Fig. 3	Locale	12S Accession	16S Accession	CO1 Accession	Source	Synonymous sample names	Location	Collector	Year
<i>Maristella_BZ_SVD</i>	BSVD	BZ	N/A	N/A	DN25384_c0_g1_i2	Transcriptome (Table S1)	BZZZDB	South Water Caye, Belize	G. Gerrish	unknown
<i>Maristella_JA_WLU</i>	JWLU	JA	DN60033_c11_g1_i1	N/A	DN60033_c11_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_JA_OBD</i>	JOBOD	JA	DN43094_c0_g1_i1	DN43094_c0_g1_i1	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_RO_RD</i>	RD	RO	DN62759_c0_g4_i1	N/A	DN58584_c0_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_JA_SVD</i>	JSVD	JA	N/A	N/A	DN43495_c0_g2_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_RO_ODH</i>	ODH	RO	DN54797_c3_g3_i3	N/A	DN13681_c0_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Vargula_FL_CGrp</i>	CGrp	FL	OL828736	N/A	OL810022	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	CGRPFlorida = HC81B	Looe Key, Florida	E. Torres and J. Morin	unknown
<i>Vargula_contragula</i>	Vcon	PA	N/A	OL828525	OL810023	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	CGRPcontragula = Contragula	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Maristella_micamacula</i>	Mmic	PA	OL828737	OL828526	OL810024	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	UGRP_micamacula = VMicaC	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Maristella_scintilla</i>	Msci	PA	OL828738	OL828527	OL810025	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	RGRP_scintilla = VSCINB	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Maristella_BZ_SVU</i>	BSVU	BZ	DN29269_c4_g2_i3	N/A	N/A	Transcriptome (Table S1)	RGRPMWU_BZ0313 = BZ0313A	Carrie Bow Caye, Belize	E. Torres and A. Cohen	unknown
<i>Maristella_noropsela</i>	Mnor	BZ	OL828739	OL828528	OL810026	Torres and Gonzalez (2007)	RGRPNoropsela = VNorop17	San Blas Islands, Panama	Jim Morin	1993
<i>Maristella_RO_AG</i>	AG	RO	DN382053_c0_g2_i1	DN382053_c0_g2_i1	DN382053_c0_g2_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				
<i>Maristella_RO_IR</i>	IR	RO	N/A	N/A	DN36910_c5_g1_i1	Transcriptome (Table S1)				

III. Expanded taxon sampling with mitochondrial genes

Figure S11. Copy of Figure 3. Expanded taxon sampling by adding individual mitochondrial genes, mainly from Torres and Gonzalez (2007) to the transcriptome data in Figure 1. We inferred this species phylogeny using the multi-species-coalescent, employed with ASTRAL-PRO (Chao Zhang et al. 2020), treating multiple mitochondrial genes as a single locus. Taxa colored pink are those that contain only mitochondrial data. Locality abbreviations are as in Fig. 1 and also include additional locations of VI=US Virgin Islands and FL=Florida USA. For *Jimmorinia* (*), we combined data from transcriptomes from a Jamaican species (cf. *J. gunnari*) with mitochondrial DNA from a specimen (*Jimmorinia* sp USVI) unidentified to species from VI. We included outgroups in the analysis, but they are not illustrated here.

Figure S9. Multi-species coalescent species tree (equivalent to Figs 3, S11) combining transcriptome data with previously published mitochondrial data. This figure has full species names rather than abbreviations. Names colored black have only mitochondrial data. Numbers at nodes are posterior probability values. See Figs 3 and S9 for detailed methods.

Figure S10. Maximum likelihood phylogeny based on mitochondrial data alone, including 12S, 16S, and *col1*. Taxa in colors use mitochondrial data from transcriptomes. We found in each transcriptome, the longest contigs with high similarity to published mitochondrial genomes of cypridinid ostracods. We then annotated the contigs using MITOS and concatenated 12S, 16S, and *col1* data with that of Torres and Gonzalez (2007) and GenBank data (see Table S5). We assumed best-fit models in IQ-TREE and searched for the ML tree. Numbers at nodes are ultrafast bootstrap and alrt support based on 1000 replicates each.

Figure S11. Ancestral state reconstruction supports a single origin of bioluminescence in Cypridinidae. Ancestral state reconstruction analysis for the presence (blue) or absence (grey) of bioluminescence. Pie charts on the nodes are scaled marginal likelihoods calculated using the ace function in APE. The asterisks denote significant nodes as defined by proportional likelihood significance tests (Pagel 1999) with a likelihood difference of at least 2 or higher.

Figure S12. Ancestral state reconstruction supports a single origin of bioluminescent courtship in Cypridinidae. Ancestral state reconstruction analysis for the presence (blue) or absence (grey) of bioluminescent courtship displays. Pie charts on the nodes are scaled marginal likelihoods calculated using the ace function in APE. The asterisks denote significant nodes as defined by proportional likelihood significance tests (Pagel 1999) with a likelihood difference of at least 2 or higher.